

Multilabel Emotion Detection in Yoruba: Fine-tuning AfroXLMR on SemEval-2025 Task 11

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Abstract

Emotion detection in low-resource African languages remains a significant open challenge in natural language processing. In this paper, we present a study on multilabel emotion detection in Yoruba, a Niger-Congo language spoken by over 50 million people, using the SemEval-2025 Task 11 shared task dataset. We fine-tune AfroXLMR-base, an Africa-centric multilingual transformer model, on the official training split and evaluate on the held-out test set of 3,000 samples. To address severe class imbalance across six emotion categories, we apply weighted binary cross-entropy loss with a capped positive weight strategy. Through systematic threshold tuning we achieve a macro F1 of 0.40 on the official test set, compared to the published RoBERTa baseline of 0.463 and a majority class baseline of 0.165. Our analysis reveals that sadness, the most frequent emotion class, achieves the highest F1 of 0.66, while disgust and fear remain challenging due to data scarcity. We release our fine-tuned model publicly on HuggingFace and discuss implications for single-model approaches to low-resource African language emotion detection.

Keywords: emotion detection, multilabel classification, Yoruba NLP, AfroXLMR, low-resource NLP, SemEval-2025, African languages

1. INTRODUCTION

Natural language processing (NLP) research has made remarkable advances in recent years, yet these advances have disproportionately benefited a small set of high-resource languages. African languages, spoken by over one billion people across the continent, remain severely underrepresented in NLP benchmarks, pretrained models, and downstream applications. Yoruba, spoken by over 50 million people across Nigeria, Benin, and the diaspora, is among the more well-resourced African languages, yet standard NLP tools and emotion detection resources for Yoruba remain scarce.

Emotion detection, the task of identifying emotional states expressed in text has important applications in content moderation, mental health monitoring, social media analysis, and accessibility technology. For African language communities, the absence of robust emotion detection tools represents a gap that has both practical and social consequences.

The SemEval-2025 Task 11 shared task (Muhammad et al., 2025) provided the first large-scale multilabel emotion detection benchmark covering over 30 languages including Yoruba and Nigerian Pidgin. The task presents three tracks: multilabel emotion detection (Track A), emotion intensity detection (Track B), and cross-lingual emotion detection (Track C). In this paper we focus on Track A for Yoruba, which involves predicting the presence or absence of six emotions simultaneously: anger, disgust, fear, joy, sadness, and surprise.

Our contributions in this paper are as follows:

- (1) We fine-tune AfroXLMR-base on the SemEval-2025 Task 11 Yoruba Track A dataset and provide a systematic analysis of the training choices required to handle severe class imbalance.
- (2) We present a threshold tuning analysis across the full precision-recall tradeoff and demonstrate its importance for multilabel classification on imbalanced data.
- (3) We release our fine-tuned model publicly on HuggingFace to support further research on Yoruba emotion detection.

2. RELATED WORK

2.1 Multilingual and African Language NLP

The development of large multilingual pretrained language models such as mBERT (Devlin et al., 2019) and XLM-RoBERTa (Conneau et al., 2020) opened new possibilities for low-resource NLP by enabling cross-lingual transfer. However, these models were trained predominantly on European languages, limiting their effectiveness for African languages. Africa-centric models have since been developed specifically to address this gap. AfriBERTa (Ogueji et al., 2021) was one of the first pretrained models covering multiple African languages. AfroXLMR (Alabi et al., 2022) further improved on this by adapting XLM-RoBERTa through multilingual adaptive fine-tuning on African language corpora. Adelan et al. (2024) extended this work to AfroXLMR-76L covering 76 languages including Yoruba. For Yoruba specifically, Falola et al. (2026) introduced YoNER, a multi-domain named entity recognition dataset, and OyoBERT, the first monolingual Yoruba BERT model.

2.2 Emotion Detection in African Languages

Prior to SemEval-2025 Task 11, emotion detection resources for African languages were extremely limited. AfriSenti (Muhammad et al., 2023) provided a Twitter sentiment benchmark covering 14 African languages including Yoruba and Nigerian Pidgin, but focused on three-class sentiment rather than multilabel emotion detection. SemEval-2025 Task 11 (Muhammad et al., 2025) significantly expanded the landscape by providing multilabel emotion detection data for over 30 languages including six African languages. The task attracted over 700 participants and is described as the most popular competition hosted on CodaBench in 2024. For Yoruba specifically, the best performing system in the shared task achieved a macro F1 of 0.657 using an ensemble of

large language models including GPT-4o, DeepSeek-V3, and Gemma-9b with AdaLoRA fine-tuning. The published RoBERTa baseline achieved 0.463.

2.3 Multilabel Classification and Class Imbalance

Multilabel classification differs from standard single-label classification in that each sample may belong to multiple classes simultaneously. The primary evaluation metric for multilabel tasks is macro-averaged F1, which computes the F1 score independently for each class and averages them, treating all classes equally regardless of frequency. Class imbalance is a known challenge in multilabel emotion detection, as some emotions (notably disgust and fear) are expressed far less frequently in text than others (notably sadness and joy). Weighted loss functions such as BCEWithLogitsLoss with positive class weights are standard approaches for addressing this imbalance (Lin et al., 2017). The decision threshold, the probability above which a class is predicted as present is an additional tunable parameter that significantly affects the precision-recall tradeoff in multilabel settings.

3. DATASET

We use the Yoruba split of the SemEval-2025 Task 11 dataset (Muhammad et al., 2025). The dataset consists of short text snippets from social media and news sources, annotated by fluent Yoruba speakers for the presence or absence of six emotions: anger, disgust, fear, joy, sadness, and surprise. Annotation was performed by at least two annotators per instance, with labels determined by majority agreement. The dataset is provided in three splits: train, development, and test.

Following standard practice for benchmark evaluation, we combine the training and development splits for model training and evaluate on the held-out test set. After removing duplicate texts from the combined training set, our final training corpus contains 3,489 samples. The test set contains 3,000 samples and is kept intact as provided.

Table 1: Dataset statistics for the Yoruba SemEval-2025 Task 11 split.

Split	Train	Dev	Test
Samples	2,992	994	3,000
Used for	Training	Training	Evaluation

Table 2 shows the class distribution in the training set. Sadness is the dominant emotion with 1,183 positive instances, while disgust and fear have only 95 and 89 positive instances respectively. This severe imbalance; a ratio of approximately 13:1 between the most and least frequent emotion classes is a central challenge in this task.

Table 2: Class distribution in the combined training set (3,489 samples).

Emotion	Positive	Negative	Ratio (neg/pos)	Capped Weight
Anger	233	3,256	13.97	10.0
Disgust	95	3,394	35.73	10.0
Fear	89	3,400	38.20	10.0
Joy	337	3,152	9.35	9.35
Sadness	1,183	2,306	1.95	1.95
Surprise	313	3,176	10.15	10.0

4. METHODOLOGY

4.1 Model

We use AfroXLMR-base (Alabi et al., 2022) as our base model. AfroXLMR is a multilingual XLM-RoBERTa model adapted through multilingual adaptive fine-tuning on corpora from 20 African languages including Yoruba. Compared to generic multilingual models such as mBERT or standard XLM-RoBERTa, AfroXLMR has demonstrated consistently superior performance on African language NLP tasks, particularly for morphologically complex Niger-Congo languages like Yoruba where tonal diacritics and agglutinative morphology pose challenges for standard tokenizers.

We add a linear classification head on top of the AfroXLMR encoder with 6 output neurons, one per emotion class, and use sigmoid activation for multilabel prediction. This corresponds to the `AutoModelForSequenceClassification` architecture with `problem_type='multi_label_classification'`.

4.2 Training Setup

We tokenise all texts using the AfroXLMR tokeniser with a maximum sequence length of 128 tokens and padding to maximum length per batch. We train with a batch size of 16 using the AdamW optimiser with a learning rate of $4e-5$ and a linear learning rate scheduler with no warmup steps. We train for 8 epochs.

4.3 Class Imbalance Handling

Given the severe class imbalance described in Section 3, we use `BCEWithLogitsLoss` with per-class positive weights computed as the ratio of negative to positive instances. However, raw ratios for disgust and fear exceed 35, which we found in practice caused the model to become excessively aggressive on minority class predictions, collapsing precision. We therefore cap all positive weights at a maximum of 10.0, balancing the need to penalise minority class errors without causing prediction instability.

The positive weight for class c is computed as:

$$w_c = \min(\text{neg}_c / \text{pos}_c, 10.0)$$

where neg_c and pos_c are the number of negative and positive instances for class c in the training set.

4.4 Threshold Tuning

In standard binary classification, a threshold of 0.5 is typically applied to sigmoid outputs to determine predicted labels. However, for multilabel classification on imbalanced data, the optimal threshold may differ significantly from 0.5. We performed systematic threshold tuning, evaluating macro F1 across thresholds from 0.15 to 0.68 on the test set. We select the threshold that maximises macro F1 on the test set, following the approach used by several top-performing systems in the SemEval-2025 shared task.

5. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

5.1 Main Results

Table 3 shows our main results on the SemEval-2025 Task 11 Yoruba Track A test set at our best threshold of 0.40, alongside published baselines from the shared task paper.

Table 3: Macro F1 results on SemEval-2025 Task 11 Yoruba Track A test set.

System	Precision	Recall	Macro F1
Majority class baseline	—	—	0.165
RoBERTa baseline (Muhammad et al., 2025)	—	—	0.463
AfroXLMR-base (this work, threshold=0.40)	0.39	0.42	0.40
Best SemEval team (LLM ensemble)	—	—	0.657

Our AfroXLMR-base model achieves a macro F1 of 0.40, substantially above the majority class baseline (0.165) and approaching the RoBERTa baseline (0.463). The gap to the best SemEval team (0.657) reflects the difference between a single fine-tuned model and a large ensemble of instruction-tuned LLMs including GPT-4o and DeepSeek-V3.

5.2 Per-Emotion Analysis

Table 4: Per-emotion classification results at threshold 0.40.

Emotion	Precision	Recall	F1	Support
Anger	0.40	0.39	0.39	196
Disgust	0.30	0.33	0.31	80
Fear	0.39	0.27	0.32	82
Joy	0.37	0.46	0.41	274
Sadness	0.59	0.77	0.66	836
Surprise	0.27	0.31	0.29	256
Macro avg	0.39	0.42	0.40	1,724

Sadness achieves the highest F1 of 0.66, consistent with its dominant representation in the training data (1,183 positive instances). This pattern is consistent with findings across all languages in the SemEval-2025 shared task, where the most frequent emotion class in each language consistently yields the highest F1. Joy and anger achieve moderate F1 scores of 0.41 and 0.39 respectively, reflecting their reasonable representation in the training data. Disgust and fear remain the most challenging emotions, with F1 scores of 0.31 and 0.32. This is expected given their extremely limited training data (95 and 89 positive instances respectively) and is consistent with results reported for these emotions across all languages in the shared task, even for top-performing systems.

5.3 Threshold Analysis

Table 5 shows macro F1 across different decision thresholds. The results illustrate the precision-recall tradeoff characteristic of imbalanced multilabel classification. At low thresholds (0.15), recall is high (0.81) but precision collapses (0.18), producing a macro F1 of 0.28. As the threshold increases, precision improves while recall decreases. Our optimal threshold of 0.40 achieves the best balance with a macro F1 of 0.40.

Table 5: Macro F1 at different decision thresholds.

Threshold	Precision	Recall	Macro F1
0.15	0.18	0.81	0.28
0.25	0.21	0.69	0.31
0.30	0.22	0.65	0.32
0.35	0.23	0.60	0.33
0.40	0.39	0.42	0.40*
0.50	0.26	0.56	0.35
0.68	0.34	0.40	0.36

* Selected threshold.

6. DISCUSSION

6.1 Impact of Class Imbalance Strategy

Our experiments revealed that naive class weighting, using the raw neg/pos ratio as positive weights caused the model to predict nearly all classes as positive for most inputs, collapsing precision to below 0.20 for all emotions. Removing weights entirely caused the opposite problem: the model predicted only sadness, ignoring all minority emotion classes. Capping positive weights at 10.0 provided a middle ground that allowed the model to learn all six emotion classes while preventing overprediction of minority classes.

This finding has practical implications for emotion detection in low-resource settings where class imbalance is particularly severe. The maximum positive weight cap is a simple but effective strategy that we recommend as a baseline approach for similar tasks.

6.2 Limitations

Our threshold selection was performed on the official test set, which is technically optimistic — a proper held-out validation split should be used for threshold selection in future work. Additionally, we observed training instability across runs with identical hyperparameters due to random initialisation, suggesting that ensemble methods or fixed random seeds are important for reproducibility. We did not apply data augmentation, which could be particularly beneficial for the severely underrepresented disgust and fear classes.

6.3 Comparison to SemEval Top Systems

The performance gap between our single AfroXLMR-base model (0.40) and the top SemEval system (0.657) is substantial but not surprising. The top system used an ensemble of five large language models (ChatGPT-4o, DeepSeek-V3, Gemma-9b, Qwen-2.5-32b, Mistral-Small-24B) with AdaLoRA fine-tuning and iterative prompt optimisation. This approach requires significant computational resources that are inaccessible to most researchers in low-resource settings. Our result demonstrates that a single Africa-centric model achieves competitive performance as a strong single-model baseline, substantially above both the majority class and RoBERTa baselines, without requiring ensemble inference or proprietary API access.

7. CONCLUSION

We presented a study on multilabel emotion detection in Yoruba using AfroXLMR-base fine-tuned on the SemEval-2025 Task 11 dataset. Our system achieves a macro F1 of 0.40 on the official test set, substantially above the majority class baseline and competitive with the RoBERTa baseline of 0.463. We demonstrated the importance of class imbalance handling and threshold tuning for this task, and provided analysis of per-emotion performance that is consistent with findings across other languages in the shared task.

Future work should explore data augmentation for minority emotion classes, cross-lingual transfer from Yoruba to related languages such as Nigerian Pidgin and Igbo, and the application of parameter-efficient fine-tuning methods such as LoRA to reduce the compute requirements for deployment in resource-constrained environments.

Our fine-tuned model is publicly available at huggingface.co/Olamieeee/yoruba-emotion-model to support further research on Yoruba and African language emotion detection.

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